

HISTORICAL SCIENCES

THE PEAK OF POLITICAL STRUGGLE IN HOI AN (QUANG NAM) VIET NAM IN 1966

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Abstract

The article focuses on researching the peak of the political struggle in 1966. In this article, the author uses two main research methods of historical science (historical method combined with logical method). In particular, the historical method will help the author present the historical picture of the research problem. At the same time, using the historical method helps the author present the historical picture of the research problem. With the historical method, the author will give the most objective comments and assessments. The completed article is based on many published sources such as documents, summary works of the Party and State, works written about the resistance war against the US (1954-1975). Especially secret documents of the Sai Gon regime are stored at National Archives Center II (Ho Chi Minh City); National Archives Center IV (Da Lat). Thereby, the article clarifies the following main issues: political struggles in Hoi An developed vigorously, particularly during the peak of the political struggle in 1966. The event in which the people of Hoi An seized control of the town for more than one month constituted a “political punch” delivered directly at the administrative center of the RVN provincial government. This struggle created favorable conditions for the subsequent development of the Hoi An revolutionary movement and contributed significantly to its eventual victory in the following years.

Keywords: *Hoi An; 1966; Hoi An Broadcasting Station; political struggle in Viet Nam.*

1. Introduction

During the resistance war against the United States for national salvation (1954–1975), political struggle played a crucial role in asserting the position of the people in direct confrontation with the U.S. war apparatus. It significantly undermined the political legitimacy of the Republic of Vietnam (RVN) government, contributed to the defeat of its strategies and tactics, and supported the armed forces in weakening enemy manpower.

Hoi An, a town with advantageous geographical and natural conditions, was selected by the United States and the RVN government as the provincial capital of Quang Nam. Numerous provincial-level administrative and military institutions were established there, including the Quang Nam Provincial Hall, military command offices, and army training centers (in Cam Ha and Cam Thanh communes), with the intention of transforming Hoi An into a strategic headquarters to suppress the revolutionary movement.

From a military perspective, in 1966 a U.S. Marine battalion of approximately 1,000 troops, after landing in Da Nang, deployed to Hoi An, establishing its command headquarters in Cam Ha commune with a force of 300 soldiers. Permanent military forces in the area included two ranger companies, two regional security companies, one naval unit, one combat police company, seven militia platoons, and numerous civil defense and youth combat units [8, p. 176].

Politically, under the strategy of “Local War,” in early 1966 the United States and the RVN government intensified the “pacification” program in Hoi An (Quang Nam), Viet Nam by consolidating and constructing Strategic Hamlet Systems (ATS) in densely populated lowland areas. To cope with the situation, the Quang Da Special Zone, Quang Nam Sub-Zone, the 51st Infantry Regiment, and security forces launched

military operations against revolutionary forces and established “new life hamlets” [15, p. 2]. In Hoi An, there were 24 strategic hamlets, concentrated in Thanh Nam, Thanh Dong, and Thanh Tay (Cam Thanh commune), Cam Pho and Ha Trung (Cam Ha commune), and Ngoc Thanh hamlet (Cam Kim commune) [15, p. 3].

Economically, the United States and the RVN government enforced an “economic blockade” strategy by intercepting and confiscating rice, salt, batteries, cloth, paper, and other essential goods destined for liberated areas.

In the cultural and educational sphere, through agencies such as the U.S. Information Service, the Chieu Hoi Information Office, cinemas, and printing facilities, various films and publications promoting violence, obscenity, and American-style lifestyles were widely disseminated from urban centers to suburban areas.

Through these military, political, economic, and cultural strategies, the primary objective of the United States and the RVN government in Hoi An was to suppress political struggles, confine the population within “New Life Hamlets,” and separate the people from the revolutionary movement. However, the harsher the repression became, the more intense the political struggles grew—culminating in the peak of political struggle in Hoi An in 1966.

2. Materials

2.1. Directives of the Party Central Committee and Local Party Organizations on Political Struggle

In March 1965, the United States implemented the “Local War” strategy by directly deploying U.S. and allied troops to the battlefield in South Vietnam. The 11th Plenum of the Central Committee of the Communist Party of Vietnam convened and issued a resolution on the urgent tasks at hand. The conference affirmed that despite changes in U.S. and RVN military

strategies, “the fundamental political objective of U.S. imperialism in South Vietnam remained the implementation of neo-colonialism; the essential nature of the war continued to be a neo-colonial war of aggression” [12, p. 598].

The Party further emphasized that “in terms of struggle methods, we must persist in combining armed struggle with political struggle, fully applying the three-pronged strategy: armed struggle, political struggle, and enemy troop mobilization” [12, p. 613].

Implementing the directives of the Party Central Committee and the Regional Party Committee of Zone V, the Quang Da Provincial Party Committee Conference (23–28 October 1966) set forth tasks for the Party, military, and people of Quang Da province: to proactively launch continuous offensives and counteroffensives through two strategic fronts and three prongs; to weaken and eliminate enemy forces; to defeat enemy sweep-and-occupy campaigns; to actively build liberated lowland rural areas and mountainous bases; to elevate both mountain and urban movements; to consolidate liberated zones; and to expand popular control in areas with U.S. troop presence [13, p. 490].

In 1966, the Hoi An Town Party Committee launched various mass movements: among children, the campaign “Small Age, Great Aspirations, Heroic Deeds”; among peasants, the slogan “Offering initiatives to eliminate the enemy, plowing with one hand and holding a gun with the other”; and among women, the “Three Responsibilities” movement—responsibility in production, family affairs, and combat support or direct participation in fighting [1, p. 247].

2.2. Typical Political Struggles in Hoi An in 1966

Entering 1966, the movement demanding the establishment of a civilian government, from March to June 1966, took place across urban areas in South Vietnam. Its deep-rooted causes lay in the policy of reprisals against Buddhism after the coup that overthrew the Ngo Dinh Diem regime (1 November 1963); the dictatorial, militaristic policies from the period of Nguyen Khanh to that of Nguyen Van Thieu; and the U.S. policy of expanding the war in Vietnam by deploying troops to the South and using air and naval forces to attack the North. The immediate trigger of the movement was the conflict within the top leadership of the Republic of Vietnam (RVN) government, when Nguyen Van Thieu and Nguyen Cao Ky dismissed Nguyen Chanh Thi—Commander of I Corps and Military Region I—and removed him from the National Leadership Committee (11 March 1966). On the same day, Thi’s supporters established the “Military–Civilian Committee of Military Region I,” openly opposing the RVN government. A widespread political struggle movement erupted throughout South Vietnam in opposition to the Thieu–Ky regime, marked by strikes, school boycotts, market closures, and mass protests in streets and schools. Seizing this opportunity, the Hoi An Town Party Committee resolved to further intensify the urban political struggle, advancing it to a new stage while placing several revolutionary cadres operating openly into key positions within the anti–Thieu–Ky committees.

The movement began in Hue with a rally of Buddhist monks, nuns, and lay followers at Dieu De Pagoda on the morning of 12 March 1966, declaring the establishment of the “People’s Force for Revolutionary Struggle” and putting forward demands to convene a constitutional assembly and to return generals to their military posts. On the same day in Da Nang, the masses—including Saigon troops—held a rally, decided to establish the “Military–Civilian Struggle Committee of Military Region I,” and raised demands similar to those in Hue.

From Hue and Da Nang, the movement spread to other urban centers in South Vietnam. In Hoi An, the political struggle reached a peak with actions demanding the establishment of a civilian government. It began on 12 March 1966, when student forces used a jeep belonging to the Quang Nam Land Office, equipped with banners and loudspeakers, to drive through the streets of Hoi An, distributing leaflets and calling for struggle to demand that the Saigon generals reinstate Lieutenant General Nguyen Chanh Thi to Military Region I.

At 2:00 p.m. on 12 March 1966, about 1,000 military personnel and civilians of Quang Nam Province gathered at the Provincial Psychological Warfare Yard for a rally organized by the Hoi An Struggle Leadership Committee. The rally presented a program of struggle demanding the return of General Nguyen Chanh Thi and called on the people and military to unite, while also requesting the central government to return General Thi to Military Region I. Finally, a local notable representing the people of Quang Nam read a petition addressed to the Lieutenant General, Chairman of the National Leadership Committee, and the Major General, Chairman of the Central Executive Committee, requesting the Quang Nam Province Chief to forward it. The petition contained three points: “Request that the Central Government return Lieutenant General Nguyen Chanh Thi to Military Region I; request that the Central Government implement the revolutionary line correctly; at any cost, the entire army and people are determined to struggle to the end” [16, p. 2]. On the same day, a Provincial Military–Civilian Struggle Committee of Quang Nam, chaired by Mr. Nguyen Dinh Hien, then Chairman of the Provincial People’s Council, distributed leaflets and notices inviting the public to attend a rally at 3:00 p.m. on 12 March 1966, to hear explanations regarding the detention of Lieutenant General Thi in Saigon, and resolutely oppose it while demanding his immediate return to Military Region I [16, p. 1]. RVN documents themselves recorded that Mr. Nguyen Dinh Hien and Quang Nam Buddhists sent two telegrams to the Lieutenant General, Chairman of the National Leadership Committee, and the Major General, Chairman of the Central Executive Committee, requesting clarification of the reason for the dismissal of Lieutenant General Nguyen Chanh Thi to end public anxiety, and warning that if by noon on 12 March 1966 no response was given, the entire population of Quang Nam would organize demonstrations [16, p. 2].

On 13 March 1966, together with many other cities across South Vietnam, the people of Hoi An simultaneously went on strike, closed markets, and boycotted schools, turning Hoi An into a “dead city.” The “Military–Civilian Struggle Committee” in Hoi An led the

political struggle, calling on the people to prepare sufficient rice and food, and directing hospitals and pharmacies to ready medicines to serve the masses. The movement showed no sign of abating; instead, it intensified. At 8:30 a.m. on 17 March 1966, some youth, officers, and soldiers of the RVN Army seized the Quang Nam Radio Station to broadcast appeals from the Provincial Military-Civilian Struggle Committee. RVN documents disclosed that the broadcasts consisted of speeches criticizing the central government and demanding the establishment of an elected government and National Assembly; similar slogans appeared on banners in the streets [3].

That same day, the people of Hoi An continued their struggle. At 4:00 p.m. on 17 March 1966, police patrols collected mimeographed leaflets calling on compatriots to strike and close markets for three purposes: “to withdraw confidence from the National Leadership Committee chaired by Lieutenant General Nguyen Van Thieu; to denounce the dictatorial, militaristic, and corrupt actions of Lieutenant General Nguyen Van Thieu and Nguyen Huu Co; and to demand the implementation of the commitment to establish an elected government with a sufficient legal basis to preserve national sovereignty and pursue a transparent policy” [5, p. 2]. RVN documents also recorded similar demands for an elected government to safeguard national sovereignty and pursue a clear revolutionary line [9, p. 1].

On 19 March 1966, the “Military-Civilian Struggle Committee of Military Region I” was transformed into the “People’s Force for Revolutionary Struggle of Military Region I,” marking a new phase of the movement. Buddhism had by then become a major force in mobilizing and organizing political struggle. Most rallies and demonstrations were either organized by Buddhists or involved large numbers of Buddhist followers. In response to the movement’s rapid growth, Nguyen Cao Ky ordered the Da Nang City Hall and the Administrative Offices of Quang Nam and Quang Tin to take all measures to “restore order.”

In Hoi An, at 3:00 p.m. on 19 March 1966, at the Quang Nam provincial lecture hall, the Unified Buddhist Church of Vietnam held a study session on Communiqué No. 21 of the Institute for the Propagation of the Dharma, attended by over 1,000 people, including youth professional associations and Buddhist followers of Hoi An. On 20 March 1966, the Quang Nam Representative Board of the Unified Buddhist Church organized another session at the Provincial Pagoda to disseminate Communiqué No. 21 [5, p. 2]. On the evening of 22 March 1966, the Unified Buddhist Church in Quang Nam met to plan the commemoration of Quach Thi Trang [4]. The next day, 23 March 1966, a rally of about 2,000 people took place in Hoi An, followed by the laying of the first stone for the Quach Thi Trang site at the junction leading into the town [7, p. 2].

As the wave of popular struggle continued to rise, on 24 March 1966 the “People’s Force for Revolutionary Struggle in Da Nang” rose up and controlled the city for 76 days and nights. In Hoi An, students and youth formed the “Youth Force for Revolutionary Struggle,” linking with workers, artisans, porters, cyclo

drivers, drivers, small traders, civil servants, and Buddhist monks and lay followers to demonstrate against the Thieu-Ky regime. On 26 March 1966, with support from Hue’s “Students Ready to Die” and students and youth from Da Nang, the Hoi An Youth Force—together with officers and soldiers of the Civil Guard, special police units, and Buddhist followers—seized the Quang Nam Radio Station, controlled major traffic routes, maintained order in the town, and launched a general strike, market closure, and school boycott. The political struggle, during which the people of Hoi An held control of the city for more than a month, was a “political blow” to the provincial center of the RVN government, creating conditions for revolutionary development against the U.S. and the Thieu regime [1, p. 252]. Unable to cope, the provincial authorities appealed to the central government. RVN documents stated that despite implementing all appropriate measures, local authorities could not end the political instability, which exceeded their capacity due to its religious dimension, and thus requested the central government to send officials with full authority to resolve the situation on the spot [4, p. 4].

On the afternoon of 1 April 1966 in Hoi An, the Quang Nam force advocating an elected National Assembly disseminated Communiqué No. 21 of the Institute for the Propagation of the Dharma. All public and private schools in Hoi An went on an indefinite strike starting 2 April 1966 [8, p. 3].

The movement demanding a civilian government continued to surge, compounding difficulties for the U.S. war effort. To create a pretext for repression, on 2 April 1966 Nguyen Cao Ky held a press conference announcing that “Da Nang has been taken over by the Communists.” He also ordered Ton That Dinh, who had replaced Nguyen Chanh Thi, to tightly control rice warehouses in Da Nang to create economic hardship and suppress the movement. On 4 April 1966, Nguyen Cao Ky sent 4,000 troops to Da Nang and deployed helicopters and L-19 aircraft to intimidate the population and drop leaflets denouncing the People’s Force for Revolutionary Struggle and calling on opposition groups and soldiers to surrender [11, p. 181].

Despite threats by the Thieu-Ky regime to use armed force, on 4 April 1966 people from suburban communes marched into Hoi An to continue the struggle. RVN documents reported increased security measures to block people allegedly incited by the Viet Cong from entering the town, ordering those without guarantees to return home, and temporarily detaining four women accused of being organized by the Viet Cong [10, p. 4].

On 15 May 1966, Nguyen Cao Ky sent 3,000 marines to Da Nang. Thieu-Ky forces seized the I Corps headquarters and the radio station, while Buddhist followers rang alarm bells throughout the city [30, p. 191]. On 18 May 1966, Nguyen Cao Ky demanded that the Institute for the Propagation of the Dharma force the struggle forces to leave pagodas in Da Nang, threatening military force if the demand was not met. On 20 May 1966, Thieu-Ky ordered attacks on the pagodas. On 23 May 1966, their forces retook Da Nang.

By the afternoon of 25 May 1966, the RVN military had regained full control of Da Nang. Around the

same time, the RVN authorities reasserted control over Quang Nam, including Hoi An. The U.S. and the RVN government implemented a combination of hardline repression and conciliatory measures to stabilize the situation. Shortly after the bloody suppression of the Central Vietnam movement demanding a civilian government—the RVN staged elections for a Constituent Assembly (11 September 1966). The people of Hoi An, notably Buddhist followers, rose up to boycott what they denounced as the sham elections of the Thieu-Ky regime.

3. Conclusion

The peak of political struggle in 1966 unfolded with remarkable intensity across southern urban centers, including Hoi An. The movement demanding a civilian government from March to June 1966, during which the people of Hoi An exercised control over the town for more than one month, represented a powerful “political punch” against U.S. and Thieu-Ky forces.

Although it did not achieve immediate final victory, the struggle held profound political and moral significance. The true victors were not those possessing superior weaponry, but Buddhist monks, lay followers, students, and patriotic citizens of Hoi An. This movement laid an essential foundation for subsequent struggles, ultimately contributing to the final victory of the Southern Vietnamese revolution. Top of Form

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